

GUTTA Glossary

Shortcuts and acronyms employed in the project

(November 19, 2021)

AB: Advisory Board

AdSP, AdSP-MAM: Autorità di Sistema Portuale del Mare Adriatico Meridionale (Southern Adriatic Sea Port Authority)

AF: Application Form

AIS: Automatic Identification System

CBC: Cross-Border Cooperation

CMCC: Centro Euro-Mediterraneo sui Cambiamenti Climatici (Euro-Mediterranean Center on Climate Change)

CMEMS: Copernicus Marine Environment Monitoring Service

CII: Carbon Intensity Indicator

CIMIS: Croatian Integrated Maritime Information System

CNRS: Centre national de la recherche scientifique

CC: Climate Change

CO: Communication Officer

CO₂: Carbon dioxide

CoC: Conditions Clearing

CoVE: Certificate of Verified Expenditure

CS: Communication Strategy

CSA: Hrvatska Udruga Brodara Mare Nostrum (Croatian Shipowners' Association Mare Nostrum)

CUP: Codice Unico di Progetto (Unique public project identifier used in Italy)

CoVE: Certificate of Verified Expenditure

DCS: Data Collection Scheme by IMO

DoC: Document of Compliance (cf Art.17 of EU Regulation 2015/757 on MRV)

DSS: Decision Support System

EC: European Commission

ECSA: European Community Shipowners Association

EE: External Expertise

EEA: European Economic Area

EMSA: European Maritime Safety Agency

EOB: End Of Business (i.e., 19:00 of a working day)

EOY: End Of Year (i.e., December 31st of current year)

ERDF: European Regional Development Fund

ETS: Emission Trading Scheme

EU: European Union

FE: Final Event(s)

FLC: First Level Control

GHG: Greenhouse Gas(es)

GV: GUTTA-VISIR

IMO: International Maritime Organization

JS: Italy-Croatia Joint Secretariat (offices in Venice, Zadar, Dubrovnik)

KOM: kick-off meeting

LP: Lead Partner

MA: Managing Authority (i.e., Veneto Region)

MC: Monitoring Committee

MMPI: Ministarstvo Mora, Prometa i Infrastrukture (Ministry Of The Sea, Transport And Infrastructure, also termed MSTI in the AF)

MRV: Monitoring Reporting Verification: EU Directive 757/2015

PRA Priority Axis (GUTTA's one is PA4 – Maritime Transport)

PA: Partnership Agreement

PMIS: Port Management Information System

PO: Project Officer (appointed by the JS)

PP: Project Partner

PSC: Port State Control

RP: Reporting Period

SC: Steering Committee

SCm1: SC meeting #1

SCm2: SC meeting #2

SCm3: SC meeting #3

SCm4: SC meeting #4

SUC: Subsidy Contract

SIU: Sistema Informativo Unificato per la Programmazione Unitaria (official web interface for submitting project information to the MA)

UNIRI: Sveučilište U Rijeci (University of Rijeka)

UniZd: Sveučilište U Zadru (University of Zadar)

VISIR: discovering Safe and efficient Routes (ship routing model employed in GUTTA)

WP: Work Package